

Project-based active learning in a robotic master's degree Subject with covid combined face-to-face and online teaching requirements

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Abstract

The work proposed here tries to introduce a project-based learning methodology for the subject Sensing Systems of the master's degree in Automation and Robotics at the University of Alicante. The heterogeneous conditions of the students and the combined face-to-face and online teaching requirements made the teachers change the current teaching model based only on theoretical classes and individual practical exercises, to a more flexible schedule following a Project-based active learning scheme. One of the problems that the teachers found in this subject and the master's degree in general is the difference in knowledge between the students in the different areas that the subject cover. This is due to the heterogeneity of students who come from different degrees from various universities and even countries. Also, in this course, the teachers must deal with the situation that the incoming students graduated in the Degree in Robotics Engineering (University of Alicante) already have most of the knowledge that this and other subjects cover. This project-based learning is therefore intended to promote self-teaching to allow the most advanced students to get a deep teaching experience while the others learn the basics of the subject. The other great challenge the teachers must deal with is the adaptation to the current face-to-face and online combined teaching classes. As the proposed projects must be carried out using the robotics laboratory hardware, a carefully designed schedule for sharing the resources was made, with special attention to the current cleaning requirements. All these factors make us think that project-based learning will allow all students to acquire the appropriate skills. To evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of this proposal two surveys were carried out, one for the students and another for the current and previous teachers of the subject. The results show how this strategy got good results even for the students with no prior knowledge of the subject area.

Keywords: Project-Based Learning; Active Learning; Computer vision Education; Project Approaches.

1 Introduction

Nowadays, engineering education all over the world pays more attention to the use of student-centered teaching methods, so that students can play a more active and collaborative role in the learning process (Lima et al., 2014 & English et al., 2012). One important active learning methodology is the designated Project-Based Learning (PBL), that has been implemented in many universities across the world (Guerra, Ulseth, & Kolmos, 2017).

In order to provide the student with active learning, PBL methodology has been chosen because it is a teaching method in which teaching and learning activities are organized around a project to achieve the desired learning outcomes of the course (Sanchez-Romero, 2019). The students, as a team, work together to solve complex computer vision problems, participate in decision making, and demonstrate leadership on a variety of tasks over a period of time to achieve project-specific deliverables. PBL can be used to improve student learning, as well as to improve student participation in the teaching/learning process and achieve higher levels of involvement (Lacuesta, 2009). PBL has also made it possible to further customize the level of entry-level learning outcomes for different entry-level engineering profiles. One of the main advantages of the PBL methodology is that it is developed in a real and experimental environment. This characteristic helps students to relate the theoretical contents with the real world, thus improving the acquisition of theoretical concepts.

At the same time, the student takes an active role in the project and sets the pace and depth of their own learning, which makes this methodology perfectly applicable to groups with disparate base knowledge.

It is not the first time that one computer vision subject is performed using a PBL methodology. Previous works (Gerónimo et al.,2013) presented a PBL scheme to form the core of the subject "Introduction to Computer Vision" of the master's program in CV and AI at the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB). (Raval M., 2019) presented a hybrid PBL and lecture-based pedagogy where only half of the presented course was developed as a PBL scheme and the other half as the common lecture-based methodology. Another computer vision course presents a hybrid PBL and deductive based learning is presented in (Khorbotly S.,2015). This last paper presented a successful PBL approach where both students and teacher were plenty satisfied but also showed a common concern of this PBL methodologies which is that the students believe than these methodologies are a way for the teachers to avoid preparing classes.

This document describes the experience acquired when introducing a Project-Based Learning (PBL) methodology in the teaching of the *Sensing Systems* subject of the master's degree in Automation and Robotics at the University of Alicante.

This paper is organized in five sections. After this introduction, the second section presents the course conditions that the proposed methodology has to deal with. The third section presents the research methodology. The fourth section show the results of the subject course. Section five presents the conclusions of the adopted methodology.

2 Course conditions

The main objective of this proposal is to develop a new didactical methodology to overcome all the new issues that the subject *Sensing Systems* of the master's degree in Automation and Robotics at the University of Alicante has this and the next years. This subject tries to describe the vision systems, ranging from the acquisition of the image to its processing in order to obtain useful features of the scene that allow the automatic control of any system, or simply the monitoring, inspection or recognition of elements of its environment. This compulsory 6 ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System) course is taught intensively in 12 sessions of 5 hours within three weeks. This is an important factor when it comes to understanding the operation of the subject and how an active learning methodology such as PBL will affect the acquisition of the different competences.

The summary of the new issues that this subject has this year:

- Covid-19 restrictions
 - Combined face-to-face and online classes
 - Limited physical assistance
 - Strict cleaning rules of class and hardware material
- Heterogenous students
 - Students with lower programming skills
 - Students with no prior knowledge on computer vision
 - Students with lower language level than expected

As most of education systems, the arrival of covid-19 strong restrictions has severely affected the development of the previously designed methodologies. The continuous changes in the restrictions made most of the coordinators and teachers to reorganize their educational model to try to give the best quality for their classes. Fortunately, the situation improved and allowed our university to adopt a combined face-to-face and online classes scheme for the whole 2020-21 academic year. This *dual model*, as they named, allowed a certain number of students in the classrooms and laboratories which allowed some subjects that work with hardware to cover some of their competences. In the case of the *Sensing Systems* subject, this allowed half of the students to be physically in class while the others being online. The other covid-19 restriction that most affected the subject was the strict cleaning rules the students and the teachers had to follow to use the class and laboratory materials which potentially reduce the usage time of the computers, robots and cameras.

On the other hand, and probably the most significant challenge, the subject had to deal with a high heterogeneity of its students. Table 1 show the different degrees that the students have. This situation is not a new one in this master's degree, but the real problem are the students coming from the Robotic engineering for the first time. Those students already completed a computer vision subject which overlap with over 80% of the contents of the *Sensing Systems*. And the previous computer vision knowledge is not the only problem as these students seem to have many other related skills that make them objectively more prepared.

Table 1. Entry profile of students enrolled in the 2020-21 academic year in the Sensing Systems subject

Degree	Number of students
Robotic Engineering	11
Electronic Engineering and Industrial Automation	6
Industrial Electronic Engineering	5
Mechanical Engineering	3
Industrial Engineering	2
Mechatronics Engineering	1
Total	28

3 Proposed Methodology

The proposed methodology is a project-base active learning scheme where the students try to accomplish some proposed projects with all the available resources and with the guidance of their teachers. The evaluation and organization scheme of the subject was therefore modified to give high importance to the development of the projects. The new organization system included some minimal theory classes to introduce all the topics of the subject for a total of 7 hours. The rest of the hours of the course (53h) were assigned to the project. The inclusion of that introduction theory classes was seen as necessary due to some students have never seen the computer vision concepts needed to at least understand the scope of the proposed projects. The evaluation of the subject was therefore defined as 25% coming from a final theory exam and the other 75% form the projects. That final theory exam was designed to assure at least some minimum knowledge of the subject topics.

The group of teaching members, including teachers from previous years, defined the design of the perception systems projects that were used to implement the project-based learning methodology. These projects have to cover the contents of the subject from a practical point of view and take into account the current conditions of semi-presence for their complexity and scope. An important aspect is the planning of access to the hardware elements necessary for the different projects (cameras, robots, etc.). Once the projects were defined, the documentation/guide for each of the projects was created so that, guided by the teachers, the groups of students were able to achieve the objectives of both knowledge application and self-learning in those necessary parts. The open nature of the projects allowed all kind of students to achieve a proper solution according to their levels.

Students were presented with a series of projects to choose from along with the documentation associated with each of them. The teachers guided the students to create groups of 3-4 trying to have groups as heterogeneous as possible (in terms of the grades they have). From there, it was promoted that the students were the ones designing and planning the tasks that they had to carry out. The supervision of the teachers was made with meetings with each group on a regular basis, in this way both the achievement of the objectives and the aptitude of this methodology was evaluated to provide the students with the required competencies.

4 Results

Research has been conducted on how PBL methodology affects final grades. It is important to remember that the main goal of this method is to better integrate different access profiles into the master's profile and not only the final knowledge that students achieved during the subject. Therefore, in this section, we will also show a summary of the final survey in which the students freely and anonymously described their main views on the methods used on the subject. To close this section, we added a discussion sub-section to evaluate and compare the results.

In order to measure the results of the proposed methodology we first analyse the students' achieved grades. This course the subject had a total of 28 students. A noticeable number of 5 students never started the subject, 3 of whom justified their abandon due to covid-19 reasons. Therefore, only 23 students participated in the subject. Figure 1 (left) shows the grade results of both the theory exam and the final Grade of the subject. The theory exam results showed that most of the students have at least the minimum concepts that the subject covers. As expected, the number of students who passed these minimal concepts exam is high. This is due that nearly half of this year student come from a degree with a similar subject. The theory average grade was 7.11. In figure 1 we can also see the final grade of the subject in both numerical and percentage ranges. The average of the final grades is 7.35 and over a 60% of the students got a mark over 7 and the rest got a mark above 5. Notice that 5 students, a 17% of the initially signed, left or never started the subject, and they were not included in these statistics but if we included them the results would change remarkably.

Figure 1. Left: Student grades of both theory exam (blue) and subject final grade (red). Right: Subject final grades percentages

As we stated before, two surveys were conducted to get the opinion of both the students and the teachers. Figure 2 shows the students survey results over 3 graded questions. The available answers to these questions varied from 1 (the lowest) to 5 (the highest) and they were expressed respectively with the labels *very low*, *low*, *medium*, *high*, and *very high*:

- Satisfaction degree: The level of satisfaction with the subject and therefore the proposed methodology.
- Effort level: The effort level that the students had to perform to achieve their mark.
- Knowledge/skills improvement: The perceived improvement of their knowledge and skills after the subject completion.

Figure 2. Student survey numerical results: satisfaction degree of the subject methodology, performed effort level and knowledge/skill improvement.

The students' results showed how they satisfaction with this methodology is above the average and nearly a 60% perceived a satisfaction above high. The effort degree got even higher percentages in the subject and 85% of students considered that this subject required a high effort.

The students' survey included an open question to include students' suggestions. One student suggested than if would have been great to have recorded classes about the whole theory content. Another one complained that his or her non previous knowledge about computer vision make him or her feel behind of his or her project peers and not being able to reach the same level in the subject time. Probably the most remarkable one was one complaining about the evaluation system of the projects because he/she was expecting a higher grade in his project due to the teachers' partial revision being positive but not having a numerical mark to regulate her/his effort to get a higher grade.

The results of the subject, which included the student grades, the completed subject projects and the student survey results, were presented to this and previous years teachers. With this information the teachers fill out the survey which included 3 graded questions with the same answer scheme than students, i.e. from 1 to 5 expressed with the labels *very low*, *low*, *medium*, *high*, and *very high*. The questions of the teachers' survey were:

- Methodology satisfaction: The level of satisfaction with the proposed methodology and the achieved results. This question in fact was the general satisfaction with the whole proposal results.
- Perceived effort: This question was not originally included in the designed survey but was added after checking the students' results. Represent the effort perceived by the teachers of the students' effort.
- Projects' scope: The level of complexity and completion of the presented projects.

Results of the teachers' survey can be seen in Figure 3. The statistics show how the satisfaction is medium-high in average. Above 50% of the teachers graded the satisfaction of the project as high or above. The perceived effort of the teachers is around medium, and the projects quality is medium-high.

Figure 3. Teachers' survey results: Methodology satisfaction, perceived students' effort and projects' scope achieved by the students.

4.1 Results discussion

Results of both subject grades and surveys were positive but there are some topics to discuss. The final grades of the subject are like previous years and other subjects of the same master. As stated before, this year was the first with students with prior knowledge of the subject but the proposed system to increase their knowledge and skills does not seem to affect the rest of the students.

The overall satisfaction of students and teachers is positive and except some 2 complains about the methodology, this proposal seems to have overcome the new conditions that the subject presented. The only concern the teachers had was a lower perceived effort from the students work in their projects but this can be derived from the covid-19 situation and the rest of conditions that made the work in groups and with hardware material even harder.

The last remarkable result the teachers want to clarify is the good quality of the projects that some groups achieved which was way better than expected. Its noticeable how some students with real interest improved their tasks inside the project and therefore, the overall project complexity.

5 Conclusion

In general, the proposed PBL methodology was satisfactory for both the students and the teachers. The achieved results even with all the challenges that the subject had this year are promising. The covid-19 restrictions and the difference in level of incoming students did not impact in the learning experience that this proposal presented. The students qualified as good the project-based learning scheme as they could use all their already owned and new knowledge to overcome the proposed projects. On the other hand, the teachers confirmed that this BPL methodology succeed the subject situation allowing to introduce some students to the basics of computer vision while allowing the most advanced student to apply state-of-the-art methods to overcome the different proposed projects. In the next years, we will continue developing this PBL approach in this and other subject of the same master's degree where we expect the same benefits.

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